

SPOT Newsletter

RE-IMAGINING Cultural tourism in Europe

SPOT PROJECT

SOCIAL AND INNOVATIVE PLATFORM ON CULTURAL
TOURISM AND ITS POTENTIAL TOWARDS DEEPENING
EUROPEANISATION

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Contents

SPOT AT GLANCE	Page 02
PROJECT NEWS	Page 03
CASE STUDY AREA NEWS	Page 07
CONFERENCES AND EVENTS	Page 16
PUBLICATIONS	Page 22
SPOT IN THE MEDIA	Page 24
TOURISM IN EUROPE	Page 25

SPOT Newsletter

Dear Reader,

We are pleased to share the second newsletter of the EU funded project SPOT, which aims to develop a new approach to understanding and addressing cultural tourism and to promote development of disadvantaged areas on the one side and propose recommendations to areas with tourism overpressure on the other one. The second issue of our newsletter presents our first research results and the progress made in the past year. The newsletter will be published annually and will contain up to date information on the project progress, recent events and news about related topics. Keep yourself informed about ongoing SPOT activities!

Enjoy the reading.

- The Editorial team

SPOT AT A GLANCE

SPOT is 3-year EU-funded project under the Horizon 2020 programme, focused on the study of issues related to cultural tourism. The consortium is composed of 15 partners from 14 European countries and Israel. Such a diverse team will bring in a wide range of knowledge, inspirations and ideas including close cooperation with the local, regional or national stakeholders. Cultural tourism has traditionally focused upon visiting “high art” museums and galleries. Our model of cultural tourism, by contrast, reflects a massive widening of cultural tourism that more accurately reflects patterns of travel in the 21st century and digital revolution in travel as a way of accessing culture.

SPOT Urban Tourism Perspectives

End of May 2021 researchers from four partner universities of the Horizon 2020 project SPOT established SPOT Urban Tourism Perspectives (SPOT UTP) thematic group. The aim of the group is to address the development and management of cultural tourism in selected European cities at a transnational level. The thematic group connects researchers from University of Barcelona, University of Ljubljana, Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra and University of Tallinn. Firstly, thematic groups will build on the existing research done within the project. Secondly, the group will do some additional research, specific to the new realities of cultural tourism in urban areas. We will keep you posted about the results of the collaboration!

Additionally, two more subgroups are active with the SPOT project: One has the focus of tourism governance being a collaboration between the University Graz, IOER and University Wroclaw, while the other is dealing with Industrial Tourism in a joint effort by the SPOT partners University Graz, University Wroclaw and University Tallinn.

PROJECT NEWS

SPOT - WEB - BASED RESOURCE CENTRE

H2020 SPOT aims to provide an innovative approach to understanding and addressing cultural tourism across regions with varying levels of tourism flow by integrating stakeholders and policy actors into the project and providing them with accessible and precise information to help decision-making. The SPOT Web-based Resource Centre as part of the SPOT Homepage is a tool designed to provide information for scientists, policy-makers, stakeholders, NGOs and practitioners in the field of cultural tourism.

This online knowledge hub aims to function as a repository of information and links for scientific and practical purposes as well. For those that seek to acquire more knowledge on cultural tourism in general and in the case study areas, the collection of external sources and the case study area map serve as a junction point to information. The searchable list of SPOT research results serves to deepen knowledge on cultural tourism in the case study areas.

The support activities of SPOT provide stakeholders, investors, researchers, government and municipal officials information on opportunities related to the development of cultural tourism and support in the quality implementation of cultural tourism development projects.

These activities can take different formats, such as policy recommendations, guidance on project implementation from formulation to monitoring. For those that seek to improve the success of cultural tourism development projects, the collection of good practices and policy recommendations helps to gain insight into successful cultural tourism policies and development programs.

The SPOT-IT tool as part of the Web-based Resource Centre is a GIS-based tool that provides decision support mechanisms for the development of cultural heritage attractions/sites in deprived remote and peripheral areas interested in establishing new, or developing existing cultural tourism sites to strengthen economic and social sustainability. The tool also seeks to indicate areas of additional development or improved sustainability in several urban areas that have historically suffered from over-tourism.

We are happy to announce that the first (BETA) version of the SPOT Web-based Resource Centre is available for internal testing using a database of external sources, a list of our research results and a compilation of information related to our case study areas.

SPOT SOCIAL AND INNOVATIVE PLATFORM ON CULTURAL TOURISM AND ITS POTENTIAL TOWARDS DEEPENING EUROPEANISATION

HOME RESOURCE CENTRE ABOUT REPORTS & OUTCOMES NETWORKING MEDIA & DOWNLOADS EVENTS & NEWS SERVICES

Q Search

Resource Centre (BETA)

The SPOT-IT tool Case study areas Good practices Services External sources Contact Us Results

Welcome

SPOT is an EU-funded project providing an innovative approach to understanding and addressing cultural tourism across regions with varying levels of tourism flow by integrating stakeholders and policy actors into the project and providing them with accessible and precise information to help decision-making. This online platform allows you to access data, maps, publications, tools, services and other information related to cultural tourism in general and in relation to the case study areas of SPOT. If you are unable to find the information you are looking for, or would like any additional information, let us know.

SPOT-IT - AN INNOVATIVE TOOL FOR CULTURAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

The SPOT-IT as part of the web-based Resource Centre is designed to provide decision support mechanisms for the development of cultural heritage attractions/sites within a given case study area. Its main aim is to enable the sustainable development of cultural tourism based on cultural tourism data taking into account the interest of multiple stakeholders as well.

The tool functions as a web-based collaborative platform and uses GIS layers that reflect numerous cultural tourism-related data in the case study areas. Based on the analyzed and processed data the tool provides outputs that help local authorities and entrepreneurs to be able to evaluate the development potential of a given cultural heritage asset and to form strategies for

establishing, promoting and marketing new and existing attractions in the chosen case study areas. It integrates multiple data resources and enables the involvement of local communities as well through a public platform.

The design of the tool has started as a specific case study for Israel and in the course of its further development will be expanded to cover all countries participating in the SPOT project. The pilot version will be available at the end of 2021.

SUMMARIZING REPORTS ON SPOT SURVEYS IN CASE STUDY AREAS

Surveys of tourists, residents and local businesses

The main objective of this study is to describe and analyse information of tourists' experiences and the views of residents and tourism entrepreneurs on the current situation and future potential of cultural tourism. Data collected during the first Covid-19 summer in fifteen different case study areas were used for assessment individually or as part of a cluster (under- or over-touristed, deindustrialised, urban and/or rural, remote peripheral or central). Three separate questionnaire surveys were conducted in each case study: for tourists, residents and tourism entrepreneurs. With these surveys we aimed to answer the following question: what similarities and differences exist in tourists', residents' and entrepreneurs' experiences and views on cultural tourism in different case study areas and what are the potentials of cultural tourism? We report the following findings:

- Transport infrastructure is considered an important issue with a lot of potential for improving the experience for tourists, residents and entrepreneurs alike.

- Both tourists and entrepreneurs often feel there is not enough information and communication provided towards tourists.
- Most residents see the economic benefits of cultural tourism. They can profit from an increased job offer, or by selling products and services. Improving facilities for tourism can also improve quality of life for residents. However, with increasing tourist numbers, residents should not be forgotten as they will have a different perspective on tourism than other stakeholders such as entrepreneurs.
- On the whole, tourists do definitely appear interested in visiting cultural attractions and sites. Local traditions/culture is an important motivator of travelling to a certain destination and it is important for most visitors to get a taste of local culture and traditions.
- Tourists are generally less satisfied about the number and diversity of cultural attractions than tourism entrepreneurs, who feel quite positive. On the other hand, entrepreneurs often feel that cultural tourism is not well developed in their case studies.

- In the urban and central case studies both tourists and entrepreneurs appear to be more satisfied about the cultural offer, and entrepreneurs also are more positive about the state of development.
- Residents are more inclined to feel that tourist numbers are (very) high in their area than entrepreneurs. This can be seen in Figure 1, where even residents of areas that are seen as under-touristed tend to feel that tourists number are (very) high. However, in general, most residents (except in mass-tourism areas) do feel that the impact of an increase of cultural tourism could be (very) positive. Also entrepreneurs see value in the increase of cultural tourism, and see an important role for the (local) authorities to help and invest. They tend to feel that tourist numbers should be higher in the area, as can be seen in Figure 2.

- Covid-19 restrictions have generally led to serious reductions especially in the numbers of foreign tourists, affecting up to 90% of tourist businesses.

Although we found patterns using the pre-defined clusters of case studies, these clusters do not appear clearly different in all aspects. Each case study has its unique characteristics, and any grouping is in a way artificial. Still, the patterns observed do emphasize some clear tendencies in the perception of cultural tourism by tourists, residents and entrepreneurs.

Figure 1: resident feeling about the number of tourists visiting the area.

Figure 2: how tourism entrepreneurs feel about the statement 'tourist numbers should be higher in this area'. NR/NA is no reply or not applicable.

CASE STUDY AREA NEWS

BUZĂU COUNTY

On June 10 2021, at the Buzău County Council the first Stakeholder Round Table with relevant national, regional and local level actors in the field of cultural tourism took place. The event was organised by the Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy (IGAR) and representatives of Buzău County Council, with the support of the Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration - coordination team of the Priority Area 3 - Culture, tourism and people to people contacts within the European Union Strategy for the Danube Region (EUSDR).

The meeting was held within WP 2. Policies, strategies, practices and planning and focused on identifying and exploring some of the key topics related to cultural tourism and with particular reference to the Case Study area: coronavirus, policy formulation, local engagement/local benefit, shared vision, sustainable development/green agenda, innovation, infrastructure/policy mix, implementation, monitoring and evaluation.

The meeting was attended by the President of Buzău County Council - Mr. Petre Emanoil Neagu, the Public Administrator of Buzău County - Mr. Alexandru Stoica, the General Director of the South-East Regional Development Agency - Miss Luminița Mihailov, the Director of the Institute of Geography of the Romanian Academy - Acad. Dan Bălțeanu, as well as the President of ANTREC Buzău, representatives of the Buzău County Council, of the territorial administrative units interested in identifying and promoting the heritage, as well as of other entities with interest in the field.

On behalf of the IGAR SPOT participated: Bianca Mitrică (Leader), Ines Grigorescu (Deputy Leader), Dan Bălțeanu, Monica Dumitrașcu, Irena Mocanu, Nicoleta Damian and Paul Șerban.

A cultural event was held in the study-area dedicated to local personalities, legends and traditions; the event was held in the locality of Cislău - Buda Crăciunești, Buzău County on 23rd September 2021. On this occasion had unveiled an information panel indicating the historical character of the road linking Buzău County to Prahova County; the road was used 400 years ago by Doamna Neaga, the wife of prominent ruler of the region (Mihnea Basarab) known as one of the great founders of churches and monasteries. The event was attended by the President of Buzău County Council - Mr. Petre Emanoil Neagu, the mayor of the Cislău Commune - Mr. Dumitru Mitroiu, the president of ANTREC Buzău - Mrs. Cristina Partal, as well as of other entities with interest in the field. On behalf of IGAR team participated the following members: Bianca Mitrica, Irena Mocanu, Nicoleta Damian and Paul Șerban.

VALLEY OF PALACES AND GARDENS, LOWER SILESIA

From June to September of year 2021 the researchers from the University of Wrocław, Poland carried-out individual interviews with key actors of cultural tourism in the case study area (Valley of Palaces and Gardens, Lower Silesia, Poland). Although summer is the peak tourist season in Poland, as many as ten stakeholders agreed to participate in the research. The meetings mostly took place at the headquarters of individual entities. The talks were led by: Małgorzata Pstrocka-Rak, Sylwia Dołzbłasz, Anna Grochowska from UWr SPOT team.

The interviewees generally answered all the questions willingly and extensively. They were particularly broad in describing the main determinants of cultural tourism development, including intersectoral cooperation in the region as well as opportunities and barriers of future cultural tourism development. The cultural heritage resources of the region were also eagerly presented by them.

Although the interviews were conducted with each stakeholder separately, the stakeholders had similar views on many of the issues raised during the interviews. They presented the Valley of Palaces and Gardens as an area with great potential for the development of cultural tourism, while acknowledging that this form of tourism faces a number of problems in its development in the region.

THE CYCLADES

In the context of case study research conducted through the SPOT project, on July 5th 2021, the University of the Aegean team held a stakeholder roundtable on cultural tourism in the Cyclades and its role in local/regional sustainable development. The Cyclades Ephor of Antiquities and representatives of the National Greek Tourism Organization (EOT) and the Cyclades Chamber of Commerce participated in the discussion which extended to the role of policy, to community involvement, and to costs and benefits to local societies from anticipated or desirable cultural tourism development, during and after the COVID-19 pandemic era. What emerged from this discussion was the utmost significance of bottom-up initiatives in culture and in tourism, in cooperative, participatory planning, management and implementation of actions, goals and visions. It was emphasized that such initiatives ought to be further developed with the patronage and support of the authorities (at all levels), including funding and infrastructure provision. Further, although significant progress had been initiated and instigated in the years before the economic and the pandemic crises, in terms of more sustainable/ 'green', innovative/ creative and technologically-upgraded cultural and cultural tourism development, this progress was put to a hold by these crises. The roundtable participants concluded with optimism for the future of cultural tourism in the Cyclades, on the basis of new apparent opportunities, commitments, interests and forward-looking dynamism, from all sides involved.

This optimism was henceforth validated in the course of this year's tourism season for the Cyclades, with the opening up of traveling and appropriate governmental measures. First estimates of international and domestic tourist arrivals so far in the Cycladic Islands for summer 2021 have surpassed those of the record year 2019, when, according to official statistical data, this number reached 994,000, climbing to over 1M. Cultural tourism accounted to a great extent for tourists' visitation motives, as culture generally constitutes a significant competitive edge of the area, in the national and international tourism industry.

STYRIAN IRON ROUTE

The Austrian team was among the various contributions to the Sustainability Special Issue 'A European Perspective on Cultural Heritage as a Driver for Sustainable Development and Regional Resilience', addressing the relationship between cultural heritage and sustainable regional development. Hereby, the researchers took a closer look at industrial heritage tourism's role in the case study area of the Styrian Iron Route. By analyzing its potential of being a driver for sustainable development, fostering social cohesion turns out to be the most important output of the utilization of industrial heritage viewed by stakeholders. Whereas economic values remain hard to quantify and at the same time questionable, the ecological component was hardly addressed and taken into account.

[A Case Study of Steirische Eisenstrasse](#)

LUSATIA

Researchers from the Leibniz Institute for Ecological Spatial Development surveyed the concerns, wishes and visions of tourists and residents in rural Brandenburg as part of an EU Horizon 2020 project 'SPOT'.

The survey results of the year 2020 from the Lieberose-Oberspreewald office are now freely available for download in an online brochure:

[Kulturtourismus im ländlichen Raum: Ergebnisse einer Besucher- und Einwohnerbefragung im Amtsbereich Lieberose / Oberspreewald \(Brandenburg\) im Corona-Jahr 2020](#)

LJUBLJANA

In summer months of year 2021 the researchers from the University of Ljubljana carried-out interviews with relevant stakeholders from culture and tourism sector. Among them were offer providers from the culture tourism sector, managing authorities, local independent tourism guides and others. The activity is part of the second work package, dedicated to the policy and institutional analysis. The interviewees shared their opinions regarding the governance of the culture tourism in Ljubljana, quality of the tourism infrastructure and cultural offer, current development and investments in cultural tourism, consequences of the pandemic on the sector, and discussed the new forms of cultural tourism in the city. The majority believes Ljubljana offers diverse cultural tourism experience of high quality, and has a tourism infrastructure of satisfactory quality. Some interviewees stated branding of the cultural tourism offers Ljubljana focuses too much on the so-called boutique tourism offer, others are of opinion this is due to a good management and a strong vision of the sector's development. All the interviewees think the local community should be more involved in all stages of the development of the cultural tourism offer, which would strengthen and endorse a greater authenticity of the offer.

The final report will be available in autumn 2021. The results of the survey with tourists, residents and businesses of the year 2020 and a summary in a brochure are available to download at the [project partner's website](#).

NITRA

On 12 May 2021, the Horizon 2020 - SPOT (Social and innovative Platform On cultural Tourism and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation) project team met with the Bishop of Nitra, prof. ThDr. Viliam Judák, PhD. The visit was associated with the presentation of copies of the monograph Religious Tourism in the Diocese of Nitra. The publication was created as a joint work of three authors from the Department of Geography and Regional Development (Krogmann, Kramáreková, Petrikovičová, 2020).

The joint discussion opened up possibilities for further cooperation between the diocese and the university - the expansion of the publication to create a work more representative in content and graphics and the joint continuation of the activities of the International European Cultural Journey of Sts. Cyril and Methodius with the aim of keeping alive the Cyril and Methodius legacy and promoting dialogue between people of different cultures and faiths. Cultural (and pilgrimage) itineraries are currently an attractive phenomenon, which is also the subject of the SPOT project. Together, we can contribute to making Nitra more visible on the cultural map of Europe.

On 20 May 2021, Stefano Dominioni, Director of the Institute of Cultural Routes in Luxembourg, announced that 5 new candidate routes have been added on the list of Cultural Routes of the Council of Europe. They also include the European Cultural Route of St. Cyril and Methodius. The newly certified cultural route of the Council of Europe is dedicated to the legacy of St. Cyril and Methodius and their direct disciples who gave birth to the Slavic cultures. In addition to the historical and cultural heritage and cultural tourism, the further development of activities within the European Cultural Route of St. Cyril and Methodius includes research, education and exchange of students between the individual countries involved. These activities are primarily managed by Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra and Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. Prof. Dr. Peter Ivanič, PhD., Chairman of the Scientific Committee of the association and Dr. Hilda Kramáreková, PhD., member of the association, completed a three-hour defense of the work presented by the scientific committee during the certification process. It also included information on the Horizon 2020 SPOT project and the joint synergetic effects of the cultural route and the project in a case study of the city of Nitra.

Within WP2 related to the Policies, strategies, practices and planning altogether 25 stakeholders were contacted, of which 16 submitted their responses or took part in the discussions. Two stakeholder round tables were held in August and September and some of the stakeholders requested background materials for the discussion, and they responded individually.

The traditional festival Nitra, milá Nitra (Nitra, Dear Nitra) was held in Nitra on July 2 – 5, 2021 on the occasion of the state and church holiday of St. Cyril and Methodius. The members of the Horizon 2020 SPOT project team were actively involved in the preparation of the event. The logo of the SPOT project was used in the information materials. At the beginning of the 2021 Nitra, Dear Nitra festival, a presentation press conference was convened in the auditorium of the Priestly Seminary of St. Gorazd on July 2, 2021 on the occasion of the certification of the European Cultural Route of St. Cyril and Methodius by the Council of Europe. The employees of Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra also informed the journalists about the certification and content of the cultural route, and the activities within the Horizon 2020 SPOT project. On Saturday, July 3, 2021, the pilgrims and friends of history set out on their journey in Dražovce and walked a section of the recently certified Cyril and Methodius route - the cultural route of the Council of Europe. This pilgrimage was held for the 5th time within the annual Nitra celebrations. The event was organized in cooperation with the Nitra Self Governing Region, the city of Nitra and the Nitra Diocese. Those who completed the itinerary received stamps in their pilgrimage passports at the individual stops, and based on these they received the Pilgrim's Certificate of Completion of the Journey and a commemorative badge at the end of the journey. Altogether 60 pilgrims and friends of history attended the pilgrimage, of which the oldest was 87 and the youngest only 8 months.

ART NOUVEAU, BARCELONA

Catalan Modernism, the Art Nouveau style central to Barcelona's architectural and cultural heritage.

This is not just a relic of the past. The popular Modernist house Casa Batlló has recently reopened its doors after extensive renovations that have brought it fully into the 21st century. Changes to the configuration of the main floor and the addition of a new floating staircase now allow for a one-way visit that reduces visitor congestion and ensures that COVID sanitary measures are easily implemented. Casa Batlló has also opened more than 2,000m² of new spaces to the public, with special immersive installations fusing art and technology that help visitors delve inside the mind of architect Antoni Gaudí and experience his inspirations firsthand. The site also features smart audioguides that turn on automatically as you enter the home's varied rooms, including a soundtrack composed specifically for the house.

In addition to this new "10D Experience", Casa Batlló also recently won a special mention from the 2021 European Award for Architectural Heritage Intervention for its 2017 restoration of the original Noble floor and the building's main façade. This balance between heritage preservation and technological innovation is a wonderful example of what makes Barcelona's Modernist sites unique visitor destinations.

SOUTH MORAVIAN REGION

The research team from Mendel University in Brno addresses important subjects from the business and state sphere of the South Moravian Region within the SPOT project of the European Union HORIZON 2020 (Social and innovative Platform On cultural Tourism and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation). Several stakeholder's meetings were organized either on-site or online by the MENDELU team from July to September 2021 in the form of a round table discussion with experts on the topics listed below:

- understanding of cultural tourism
- Impacts of Covid19 on cultural tourism
- tourism policy at local/regional/national level
- involvement of local citizens (opportunities, benefits)
- tourism infrastructure (accommodation, catering facilities, transport)
- Sustainable Development
- vision of cultural tourism development (what we would like to achieve)
- innovation (improving the quality of the offer, reaching new customers)
- implementation (interconnection of public and state administration in the field of tourism)
- monitoring and evaluation of tourism (number of visitors, interest in cultural attractions)
- other (at discretion)

The acquired information will be elaborated and proposed to be implemented in particular forms into European, regional or local policies focused on cultural tourism.

The local and regional tourism development policy is also possible to influence through cooperation among the entities within the South Moravian Region by offering the possibility of using the innovative SPOT-IT tool to facilitate decision-making processes in this area, among others.

The research team of Mendel University in Brno organized already the third roundtable on the topic of cultural tourism. In July, August and September, these meetings were attended by important stakeholders operating in the field of tourism within the selected case study area such as representatives of museums, tourism guides, tourist associations, tourist information centres, project and marketing managers, academic staff and teachers, local action group managers and employees and officer of the regional development department of the South Moravian Region. The topics of cultural tourism and its situation during the COVID-19 limitations (experienced changes, new opportunities, etc.) were discussed. Policies, infrastructures or shared visions within cultural tourism were also discussed, as well as other topics. The SPOT-IT tool prototype version as part of the SPOT project was introduced during the meeting. All stakeholders showed high interest to test it soon and give us their feedback.

KOMÁROM-KOMÁRNO

The Sustainability Special Issue "A European Perspective on Cultural Heritage as a Driver for Sustainable Development and Regional Resilience" provides a state-of-the-art overview of contemporary cultural heritage management within Europe, providing theoretical contributions as well as practical toolkits and case studies. Contributions will help to frame cultural heritage as a resource for the creation of sustainable and resilient territories.

Members of the H2020 SPOT Consortium contributed to the Special Issue with several articles. Partners examined the phenomenon of media-related tourism (by Stephanie Garrison and Claire Wallace), analysed the perceptions of diverse significant actors regarding culture and tourism during the COVID-19 pandemic (by Giovanna Rech and Lorenzo Migliorati), investigated the recent changes in cultural tourism in urban areas and addressed alternative cultural tourism products to diversify the offerings (by Alfred Krogmann, Peter Ivanič, Hilda Kramáreková, Lucia Petrikovičová, František Petrovič and Henrich Grežo), investigated industrial heritage tourism in the context of sustainable development (by Jörn Harfst, Jasmin Sandriester and Wolfgang Fischer), assessed the sustainable development of tourism and the territorial inequalities at a micro-scale based on a sustainable tourism index (by Bianca Mitrică, Paul-Răzvan Șerban, Irena Mocanu, Nicoleta Damian, Ines Grigorescu, Monica Dumitrașcu and Cristina Dumitrică), investigated cultural tourism as a driver of rural development (by Milada Šťastná, Antonín Vaishar, Jiří Brychta, Kristýna Tuzová, Jan Zloch and Veronika Stodolová) and examined cross-border cultural tourism as an indicator of territorial integration (by Tamás Hardi, Marcell Kupi, Gyula Ocskay and Eszter Szemerédi).

The research team from CERS Institute for Regional Studies, Győr, Hungary held its first Stakeholders' Roundtable within the SPOT project of the European Union HORIZON 2020 (Social and innovative Platform On cultural Tourism and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation) on the 4th of August.

Key actors of cultural tourism were invited to discuss impacts of COVID-19 on cultural tourism in the cross-border area, tourism policy at local and regional level and shared visions of cultural tourism development across the border.

The iconic cultural tourism site of the region, the Monostor Fortress served as location for the First Roundtable. The representative of the organization responsible for the development of cultural tourism and city marketing in Komárom provided insight on future development paths related to tourism infrastructure, the managing director of Ponsdanubii EGTC shared current and future cultural tourism development projects across the border and the cultural director of the Fortress shared current and possible ways to increase engagement of cultural tourists.

Partners discussed enhancing the role of Danube in cultural tourism, opportunities and barriers of cultural tourism development and the possibilities of using the innovative SPOT-IT tool to facilitate decision-making processes in the area.

The Second Roundtable will be held at the end of August in Komárno, organized with the help of Ponsdanubii EGTC.

The West-Hungarian Research Department of the CERS Institute for Regional Studies hosted the staff of the Romanian Academy, Institute of Geography from 8 to 14 November 2021. The visit took place in the framework of a bilateral cooperation between the Hungarian Academy of Sciences and the Romanian Academy. Both Research Institutes are partners of the Horizon 2020 SPOT (Social and innovative platform on cultural tourism and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation) project. During the field trip to the case study area, we visited cultural tourism destinations in Komárom, Hungary, and Komárno, Slovakia as well, including the Fort Monostor and its Museum on the past of the Danube navigation and the newly opened Fort Csillag, which is the new home of the Hungarian Museum of Fine Arts' plaster cast collection.

IDA-VIRUMAA

Following a long period of Covid-19-related restrictions, Ida-Virumaa was finally opened to tourists for the summer in summer 2021. In September 2021, after the peak tourism season, Saara Mildeberg from the University of Tallinn (TLU) carried out individual interviews with key actors in cultural tourism in the case study region. For the interviews which were conducted in the framework of SPOT WP 2, 13 stakeholders agreed to give their opinion on the potential of cultural tourism in the region, giving their definition of the phenomenon and shedding light on its success stories and obstacles. A relevant topic was also the so-called Green Turn with the just transition from the oil shale industry, and its impact on cultural tourism and tourism in general. Although the topic is widely discussed in the region, there is still a lot of confusion about the future, and how the changes will affect cultural tourism.

The interviews took place both in-person and online and the interviewees were enthusiastic to elaborate on their experiences before the pre-pandemic and during current times and give suggestions on how to improve the current situation. The data collected was later analysed into a joint report.

PIEDMONT LANDSCAPE AND LITERARY PARK

In 2022, two important events related to tourism and culture will take place in the Langhe Monferrato and Roero case study areas. From March 2022 to March 2021, the centenary of the birth of the book author and partisan "Beppe Fenoglio 22" will be celebrated: Literature will merge with theatre, music, history and visual arts. The sixth edition of the "Global Conference on Wine Tourism", the world conference launched in 2016 and promoted by the United Nations World Tourism Organisation, will be held in Alba in September.

Both events will bring together the Langhe Monferrato and Roero area with national and international experts, practitioners and an enthusiastic public to reflect on the present and future of its rich heritage: landscape, people, products of the earth, intellectuals, writers, monuments and their multiple values. The UNIVR team with the SPOT project is listening to stakeholders to be an engaged observer of both initiatives.

[UNWTO initiative on Wine Tourism](#)

[Co-organiser of the Conference is local DMO](#)

[Centenary "Beppe Fenoglio 22"](#)

CONFERENCES AND EVENTS

More information: <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/blog>

SPOT: A Strong Role for Tourism Stakeholders. Rural Connections Webinar

SPOT project was presented during the webinar entitled "Rural tourism and marketing" organised by RURITAGE. The presentation is divided into three parts: firstly, SPOT project and activities carried the first year of the project; secondly, a focus on the Italian case study, trying to underline the efforts of involving stakeholders despite the Coronavirus situation; thirdly, after consultation with the 15 Partners, it is offered an insight on issues of inclusiveness, biodiversity and equal involvement of local communities.

The UNIVR Team has represented SPOT project during the RURITAGE webinar on "Rural tourism and marketing". Before the webinar, it has been launched an internal consultation on issues addressed to SPOT project by the Organisers. This document will display an insight on Consortium understandings and evidences on issues of inclusiveness, biodiversity and equal involvement of local communities.

Contradictions Shaping Urban Futures

European Urban Research Association (EURA) held on May 6th and 7th 2021 on-line its annual conference on the topic of "Contradictions Shaping Urban Futures". David Klepej and Naja Marot, two researchers from the Department of Landscape Architecture participated with the presentation 'Urban tourism and its social impacts: the case of Ljubljana, Slovenia'. In their contribution, they compared the social impacts of urban tourism detected through Territorial Impact Assessment (TIA) with those perceived by the residents in annual surveys about tourism in Ljubljana. TIA has proven to be more sensitive in terms of the variety of detected and covered impacts and more objective due to the several steps of the assessment process. Both methods still show that the positive impacts of urban tourism had before 2019 outweighed the negative ones. Presentation is the result of work on projects: MESTUR (Analysis and governance of spatial and social impacts of urban tourism in the case of Ljubljana and Maribor), financed by Slovenian Research Agency, and SPOT (Social and Innovative Platform on cultural tourism and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation), financed by the h2020 programme.

SPOT
RE-IMAGINING
Cultural Tourism in Europe
A Strong Role for Tourism Stakeholders

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UNIVERSITÀ di VERONA

On behalf of the SPOT Consortium | Coordinated by MENDELU

TOURMAN 2021

On May Sylwia Dołzbłasz and Małgorzata Pstrocka-Rak from the Polish team attended an international conference on tourism.

The 4th International Scientific Conference "TOURMAN 2021" took place online, on the 21st to 23rd of May 2021 and was themed "Restarting tourism, travel and hospitality: The day after". It was organised by the International Hellenic University.

This year there were 1.104 registered delegates and 521 presentations at TOURMAN 2021. According to the organizers this was the largest international scientific conference on tourism ever.

During the Saturday morning session devoted to cultural and heritage tourism, Małgorzata Pstrocka-Rak delivered a presentation titled: The past for the future. Significance of cultural heritage for future tourist development in disadvantaged areas. The presented research results are related to the implementation of the international SPOT project, conducted by the team of researchers from the University of Wrocław, Poland.

During the session dedicated to 'Cultural and heritage tourism', University of the Aegean presented the variable impacts that the COVID-19 pandemic and restrictive measures imposed on travellers and tourism businesses in three Aegean islands (Andros, Syros, Santorini), and specifically how the pandemic altered a) tourists' travel choices, behaviour and preferences with regard to their cultural site visits and event attendance and b) approaches of tourism related businesses and entrepreneurship towards cultural tourism in the three islands. The findings indicated that, despite the broadly acknowledged role of culture in tourism, tourists showed particular interest for outdoor cultural sites, or visits to smaller-scale events in less crowded locations.

Conservation of Cultural and Heritage Landscape

Prof. Irit Amit Cohen, a member of SPOT project heritage 2020 (WP3, Bar Ilan team), was one of the organizers of the conference and was invited to give the opening lecture.

Her lecture title was: New trends in characterization and management of cultural landscapes. The main issue focused on cultural and heritage tourism in open space and cultural landscapes and the recognition of the need for integrated management.

In her lecture she described the change that has taken place in the status of cultural landscapes, the growing demand for tourism in these landscapes and the new ways of managing them - management that emphasizes the similar values and characteristics that natural landscapes, agricultural landscapes and cultural heritage assets have.

The case study was the Valley of the Springs and the city of Beit She'an which is the case study area of WP3. Prof. Amit Cohen presented findings from the study area, collected through questionnaires and interviews, and she emphasized that these findings are part of a larger research, the SPOT project, in which several European countries are partners.

6th Heritage Forum of Central Europe

SPOT providing answers at the Heritage Forum: Can sustainable development be fostered through industrial heritage tourism?

This question was raised and discussed at the 6th Heritage Forum of Central Europe in June by the

Austrian SPOT team. Their contribution highlighted that industrial heritage tourism is often only a niche product, difficult to valorize. Furthermore, industrial regions often suffer from a 'dirty image' and weak touristic infrastructure, creating a difficult starting point at a highly competitive tourism market. The case study shows these typical shortcomings with a fairly large number of visitors who are not satisfied, with the region struggling to meet the cultural tourist's needs. On the other hand, industrial heritage is an important carrier of regional identity and its valorization can foster social cohesion, an important component of sustainable development.

International Geographical Union

Between 12 and 14 August 2021, the researchers from IGAR team attended the International Geographical Union (IGU) Pre-congress seminar on Local and Regional Aspects of Natural Hazards which was held in Varna, Bulgaria. The event was organised by the Commissions for Local and Regional Development and Land Use and Land Cover Change at the International Geographical Union (IGU) and the Bulgarian National Science Program "Environmental Protection and Reduction of Risks of Adverse Events and Natural Disasters".

On this occasion, some of SPOT project results were disseminated within the paper entitled: The Impacts of Covid-19 Crisis on Local Cultural Tourism. Evidence From Buzău Carpathians and Subcarpathians (Romania). Authors: Mitrică B., Grigorescu I., Damian N., Șerban P-R., Mocanu I., Dumitrașcu M., Dumitrică C.

Tourism in Southern and Eastern Europe

Researchers from Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy also attended the conference ToSEE - Tourism in Southern and Eastern Europe. On behalf of the IGAR team, the paper on Developing an indicator-based framework to measure sustainable tourism in Romania. A territorial approach, authors: Bianca Mitrică, Paul-Răzvan Șerban, Ines Grigorescu, Nicoleta Damian, Irena Mocanu, Monica Dumitrașcu, Cristina Dumitrică was presented.

Association of Regional Sciences

The SPOT Italian case study was presented at the XLII Annual Scientific Conference of Italian Association of Regional Sciences (A.I.S.Re) entitled Territorial challenges in the post-covid era (Web Conference, 8-10 September 2021) during the session Opportunities, risks and challenges of the digital transformation of tourism: between sustainability and sharing.

The paper "Resilient territories and digital landscapes: cultural tourism in the Langhe, Roero and Monferrato", presented by Giovanna Rech on behalf of the University of Verona team, discussed the local community's representations of cultural tourism as a vector of resilience for the territory and the stakeholders' commitment to promote and enhance cultural resources, starting from the destination digital reputation.

Urban planning through the prism of pandemics

On September 17th, 2021, the Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geodesy of University of Ljubljana hosted the 32nd Sedlar's conference. This is the annual conference of Slovene Town and Spatial Planning Association of Slovenia. This year's conference was titled »Urban planning through the prism of pandemics – challenges and guidelines«, so the speakers elaborated, reflected and presented the results of the research focuses on the pandemic impacts on the space (urban, rural, suburban). Assistant Professor Naja Marot from the Department of the Landscape Architecture talked about the city of Ljubljana and the impacts of urban tourism on the city before and during the pandemics, specifically. Together with the colleagues she presented the outcomes of the interviews with the tourism suppliers in the year 2020 (project MESTUR, financed by the Slovenian Research Agency) and the survey with the tourists, queried in the summer 2020 in the project SPOT. The conference wrapped up with the conclusions about the adaptation of the spatial and urban planning in the times between and after the crises, such as the pandemic one is.

European Network for Housing Research Conference

On September 2, researchers Danielle Bishop, Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway, and Montserrat Simó represented the University of Barcelona's team at the European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) 2021 Conference. During the online presentation of their paper titled "Sustainable Communities and Housing in Contested Cities: The Case of Residents and Tourists in Barcelona", they introduced the SPOT project and examined the effects of short-term tourist rentals on Barcelona's residential housing and rental markets, as well as offering policy considerations for the city's relationship with tourism in the post-COVID future. This paper integrated research undertaken through several of the SPOT project's work packages, including findings from a survey carried out with local residents (WP1) and analysis of public policy responses to the pandemic in the tourism, cultural, and economic sectors (WP2). The Q&A session afterward also provided a fruitful opportunity to highlight two of the SPOT project's missions: expanding our understanding of what constitutes cultural tourism and identifying areas of either potential development or greater sustainability in tourism.

Tourism in Southern and Eastern Europe

Several SPOT partners participated in the special session on smart solutions for sustainable cultural tourism development in the post-COVID-19 era involving the contributions from 3 #HORIZON2020 projects. The session was part of the hybrid #ToSEE2021 conference.

One of the online presenters was prof. Milada Šťastná from MENDELU (CZ), coordinator of SPOT HORIZON2020 project with the presentation called “Why are two destinations with high cultural potential completely different on the tourism market: the case studies of Dolní Kounice and Lednice (Moravia)” showing part of the Czech case study area results.

Also, researchers from the Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Landscape Architecture attended the scientific conference ToSEE, this year subtitled as ToSEE – Smart, Experience, Excellence and ToFEEL – Feelings, Excitement, Education, Leisure. The conference was organised in a hybrid form in Opatija, Croatia, by the Faculty of Tourism Hospitality Management at the University of Rijeka. David Klepej presented the paper “Urban Tourism and its Consideration in Strategic Spatial Planning in Selected Middle-Sized Central European Cities” and Naja Marot described the “Supply-Side Implications of COVID-19 Pandemic for Urban Tourism in the Middle-Sized European Cities”. The first presentation derives from the analysis of the territorial governance of tourism in the Central European cities, performed in the frame of the MESTUR project (<http://arhiv.bf.uni-lj.si/oddelek-za-krajinsko-arhitekturo/oddelek/raziskovalno-in-strokovno-delo/projekti/mestur/>), which is financed by the Slovenian Research Agency. The second presentation focused on the response of the tourism providers on the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, done in the project SPOT, financed by the Horizon 2020 programme.

Danielle Bishop also presented the paper "The End of 'Business as Usual'? Reimagining Barcelona Tourism after COVID-19" at the ToSEE conference. This paper, co-authored with Dr. Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway and Dr. Montserrat Simó, analyzed the changes COVID-19 has wrought on Barcelona's tourism sector up to the present. The authors also consider cultural tourism as a potential way forward to improve some of the negative externalities of tourism in the city in the post-COVID future.

ECRCM

Members of Slovakian SPOT team (prof. Ivanič and dr. Kramáreková) take part in General Assembly Meeting of Association European Cultural Route of Saints Cyril and Methodius (ECRCM) held on 6 October 2021. The aims of meeting were (except other information) Proposal of the international strategy of the CM Route – Cultural route of the Council of Europe in progress and ECRCM Scientific Committee - scholarly basis of the CM Route. Prof. Ivanič and dr. Kramáreková have been cooperated on this document.

Days of Innovation and Research Conference

The SPOT project and Cycladic case study area were presented and discussed in the context of University of the Aegean research and innovation activities, by the SPOT UAegean team, in this Conference organized on the 19th and 20th of April 2021 by the University of the Aegean, for local/ regional entrepreneurs, institutions, research organizations, and public authorities (of various levels) in the Aegean region. The scientific contribution of SPOT, as well as its practical and anticipated contribution to cultural tourism in terms of entrepreneurial support and anticipated development through the SPOT-IT tool, were greatly appreciated by the Conference participants, including the Director of the

Organization of Greek Tourism Entrepreneurs and main tourism statistical service of Greece (INSETE), who showed special interest in the application of the tool and other research deliverables of the SPOT project in the cultural tourism sector.

14th International Conference for Cultural Tourism in Europe "Regenerating European Tourism through Culture, Heritage & Creativity"

Sylwia Dołzbłasz, Together or apart – natural values and cultural heritage in the development of tourism in the Valley of Palaces and Gardens in Poland, 14th Conference for Cultural Tourism in Europe "Regenerating European Tourism through Culture, Heritage and Creativity", European Cultural Tourism Network, 21-22 October 2021.

Also participated:

IGAR - Bianca Mitrică, Ines Grigorescu Nicoleta Damian, Paul-Răzvan Șerban, Irena Mocanu, Monica Dumitrașcu, Cristina Dumitrică: COVID-19 pandemic and the new challenges of cultural tourism. An analysis of Buzău Carpathians and Subcarpathians (Romania)

UWR - Sylwia Dołzbłasz: Together or apart – natural values and cultural heritage in the development of tourism in the Valley of Palaces and Gardens in Poland

UAegen - Georgoula V., Terkenli S. T.: Culture and creative tourism in the Cyclades: a critical overview on regenerating tourism.

International Geographical Congress

Eszter Szemerédi represented the research team from CERS Institute for Regional Studies, Győr, Hungary on the 16th of August at the 34th International Geographical Congress with the paper „Strengthening cohesion in cross-border cultural tourism destinations through digitalization”. She presented the findings of the residential and tourist survey carried out within the framework of SPOT project, with special focus on cohesion in cross-border tourism destinations and the use of digital elements in cross-border cultural tourism in the case study area of the Komárom-Komárno cross-border city.

Other participations

- Monthly seminar of the Network Patrimonialitté on heritagisation of literature (2020-2021; 2021-ongoing)
Participating partner:
UNIVR – Giovanna Rech
- Young Regionalists Conference (2021.10.01-02.) Participating partner: KRTK Csányiné Szemerédi Eszter – Kupi Marcell – Hardi Tamás:
Promoting the integration of cross-border cultural tourism destinations through digitalisation
- European Week of Regions and Cities (#EURegionsWeek) (2021.10.11-15.)
Participating partner:
IGAR - Bianca Mitrică: Sustainable tourism as development factor in Romanian border regions.
- EU-JPI project "Curbatheri-Deep Cities" (2021.05.04)
Participating partner:
UB – Danielle Bishop
- ToSEE – Tourism in Southern and Eastern Europe 6th International Scientific Conference (2021.06.30-07.02.)
Participating partner:
UB - Danielle Bishop, Montserrat Pareja-Eastway, and Montserrat Simó Solsona: The End of 'Business as Usual'? Reimagining Barcelona Tourism.
- The 5th International Conference: INDUSTRIAL HERITAGE CONSERVATION, CULTURAL PROMOTION AND INTELLIGENT REUSE (2021.09.23-24.)
Participating partner:
IGAR - Ines Grigorescu, Bianca Mitric: The adaptive (re)use of post-communist industrial sites in Bucharest. Between urban development and heritage conservation
UNIGRAZ - Kern, C. Sandriester, J. Harfst, J.: Promotion of industrial heritage and tourism as regional potential
- The 32nd Sedlar's Conference (2021.09.17.)
Participating partner:
UL - Naja Marot, David Klepej, Irena Ograjenšek, Manca Krošelj, Nina Stubičar (all UL) and Uroš Horvat (UM - University of Maribor): The challenges of urban tourism in the pandemic times in the City Municipality of Ljubljana. Naja Marot
- Distance training for "Sliding Doors" (Co-funded by the Europe for Citizens Programme of the European Union, Scientific coordinator: Frédéric Spagnoli, Université de Franche-Comté, France) (2021.06.08)
Participating partner:
UNIVR - Giovanna Rech (trainer): The mosaic of migration(s) / An introduction to the methodology of questionnaires and interviews
- Course of Sociology of tourism (advanced), Global and Local Studies/Master Degree, track (2021.09.14-ongoing)
Participating partner:
UNIVR: Giovanna Rech (trainer)
- Training EUHeritage MOOC. (2021.06.21-2021.09.30)
Participating partner:
UNIVR – Giovanna Rech
- SmartCulTour „The future of urban tourism“ (2021.11.26) Participating partner:
UL – Naja Marot
- University of Padova, Department of Historical and Geographic Sciences and the Ancient World (DiSSGeA), Geography of tourism: heritage and sustainability (2021.11.17.)
Participating partner:
UAegean - Theano S. Terkenli (open lecture): Cultural tourism in times of change: patterns and prospects from the Cyclades, Greece

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- UL (2021): Summary of the WP1 report on survey with tourists, residents and businesses in year 2020
- UKF (2021): Univerzita súčasťou certifikácie Rady Európy = Constantine the Philosopher University as a part of certification by the Council of Europe

SPOT IN THE MEDIA

Under the auspices of the Portuguese Government, and with full collaboration from the Slovenian Government, H2020 IMPACTOUR Project was proud to announce the ReDiscover Europe Workshop, providing an unique opportunity to discuss the role of sustainable Cultural Tourism in today's Europe in a post-COVID era. The SPOT project was represented by Mendelu (Milada Šťastná). The workshop was recorded, the SPOT presentation starts on timing: 5:21:36.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=snD4gXQsjQQ>

On Friday, June 4th 2021, Professor Theano S. Terkenli from the University of the Aegean (UAegean team) was invited, by Athens' radio journalist Giorgos Apostolidis, to speak on air (FM Radio Athens 98,4), about, among other related subjects, the prospects and the significance of cultural tourism in Greece and beyond. In particular, the [interview](#) focused on the aims and objectives of the H2020 SPOT project and the potential uses of the innovative SPOT IT TOOL, aiming to develop a new approach to understanding and addressing cultural tourism in the case study areas (e.g., the islands of Syros, Andros and Santorini) of the Cyclades.

In October 2021, the research team from the University of the Aberdeen released a short film about the media tourism in one of their case study areas, the village of Doune. Their video included interviews with a wide range of tourist stakeholders in the area including representatives of the hospitality industry, tour operators, policy makers and the conservation charity.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q-8liCR4yZ4&t=1s>

TOURISM IN EUROPE: COVID-19 AND BEYOND

Innovative solutions during the pandemic and the way to a more resilient cultural tourism

According to the UNWTO, due to the pandemic international arrivals dropped by 74% in 2020 and tourism destinations welcomed 1 billion fewer visitors. Europe has been one of the most effected regions with over 500 million fewer international tourists. While cultural tourism makes up nearly 40% of world tourism revenues, the pandemic has shown that the full extent of the economic contribution of cultural sector has been underestimated. While physical distancing and travel restrictions greatly affected the traditional ways of consuming culture, it has also created opportunities to move towards a more resilient, inclusive and resource efficient model of cultural tourism, which can contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals (UNWTO 2021).

Many communities found ways to adapt to the circumstances and harnessed technology to make cultural tourism more competitive. Besides individual countries announcing support funds, providing online tours of their most visited destinations and rebooting their cultural life initiatives like the social media campaign, #ShareOurHeritage and the ResiliArt movement by UNESCO aimed to promote access to culture and to enhance dialogue in a digital way.

The UNESCO pivoting their work from immediate impact assessment to long-term changes and solutions collected good examples on how to „build back better” in the following years in a way that culture becomes a central element in sustainable tourism development, which resulted in a series of publications named “Culture and COVID-19 – Impact and Response Tracker” (UNESCO 2020a).

#ShareOurHeritage

In 2020 the UNESCO with the support of Google Arts & Culture launched an online exhibition featuring World Heritage sites from across the globe, providing first-hand accounts from World Heritage site managers as well (UNESCO 2020b).

The UNWTO similarly to the UNESCO focused more on recovery in the last year and published a list of recommendations. The focus of their recommendations is on promoting synergies between tourism and culture, on the exchange of good practices and on the creation of a participatory governance with the invitation of artists, professionals, local communities, the private sector and destination representatives. The UNWTO emphasizes the importance of open discussion on a responsible cultural tourism, which in their viewpoint means a comprehensive place-based approach for cultural tourism, the re-discovery of local culture, the promotion of local ways of life and the revival of urban and rural experiences. „Building back better” should include the digital upskilling of tourism workers, and forming alliances with technology and media partners. The list of recommendations treats the protection of nature as a key element of safeguarding local culture, which not only means the protection of natural heritage and biodiversity, but the education of visitors and locals about the importance of it as well (UNWTO 2021).

[UNWTO \(2021\): Inclusive Recovery Guide – Sociocultural Impacts of Covid-19, Issue 2: Cultural Tourism.](#)

ResiliArt Debate

The ResiliArt movement of UNESCO launched in 2020 brings together artists and cultural actors to discuss the impact of the pandemic on culture. “It is designed to inform the development of policies and financial mechanisms that can help creators and communities overcome the crisis” (UNESCO 2020b).

[UNESCO \(2020a\): Culture and COVID-19. Impact & Response Tracker. Special Issue.](#)

[UNESCO \(2020b\): UNESCO supports culture and heritage during COVID-19 shutdown.](#)

Roll-up, leaflets and more dissemination materials:
<http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/media-and-downloads>

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